

QUALITY OF SHEEP MEAT IN SILVOPASTORAL MEADOWS

1. Flock of sheep above the tree line in Mount Timfristos (alt: 2000m), Photo G. Bakogiorgos 2. Flock of sheep in the Xiromero oak forest (winter 2024)
3. Flock of sheep in silvopastoral meadow in Sivista near lake Kremasta Photo G. Bakogiorgos 4. Sheep grazing in W. Evrytania, Photo A. Papadopoulos

WHAT AND WHY

Numerous studies have compared the quality of meat from semi-extensively reared sheep and lambs to that of animals raised under intensive systems. Overall, grazing animals—particularly those raised on biodiverse wooded grasslands—tend to produce meat of superior quality, with several notable advantages: i. Improved fatty acid profile, characterized by higher concentrations of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), especially conjugated linoleic acid (CLA), which is associated with various health benefits. ii. Favorable cardiovascular health markers, including improved atherogenic (AI) and thrombogenic (TI) indices. iii. Lower $\omega 6/\omega 3$ fatty acid ratio, which is considered beneficial in reducing inflammation and promoting cardiovascular health. iv. Enhanced oxidative stability of fats, evidenced by reduced levels of malondialdehyde (MDA), a marker of lipid peroxidation, expressed in ng/g. v. Superior sensory attributes, such as a bright red color (indicated by higher a^* values using the CIE color system), a pleasant aroma, and a smoother, more complex taste. However, there are some drawbacks to meat from free-range systems. It is often slightly tougher in texture, and the fat tends to be more watery due to the higher PUFA content.

Keywords: grazing, PUFAs, MDA

HOW THE CHALLENGE IS ADDRESSED

To fully benefit from grazing systems, sheep must be able to access forage without having to travel long distances. Excessive movement not only stresses the animals but also negatively impacts their energy balance, ultimately leading to tougher meat and reduced meat quality.

In wooded pastures, optimal conditions involve allowing sheep to graze freely under the supervision of a shepherd, ensuring they have access to adequate water and salt points. Trees play a vital role in these systems by providing shade in the summer and shelter from harsh weather in the winter, enhancing animal welfare and maintaining productivity.

To minimize the need for concentrated feed, the grazing period should be extended for as long as possible, ideally year-round where climate and pasture conditions permit. This approach not only supports meat quality but also contributes to more sustainable and natural livestock management.

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ADVANTAGES

Free grazing of sheep in forest meadows plays a crucial role in enhancing the quality of sheep meat, while also offering significant ecological and animal welfare benefits.

Meat Quality Benefits:

Meat from sheep raised in silvopastoral systems exhibits several nutritional and sensory advantages:

- **Higher levels of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) and generally lower levels of saturated fatty acids (SFAs)**, resulting in a more favorable PUFA/SFA ratio.
- **Lower $\omega 6/\omega 3$ fatty acid ratio**, approaching the ideal 4:1 ratio that was typical in diets prior to the intensification of livestock farming in the 20th century.
- **Reduced atherogenic (AI) and thrombogenic (TI) indices**, indicating a lower risk of cardiovascular disease.
- **Lower malondialdehyde (MDA) values** (expressed in ng/g), reflecting greater oxidative stability, which reduces the potential for mutagenic effects.
- **Improved sensory characteristics**, including a **bright red color, pleasant aroma, and a mild, smooth taste.**

Environmental and Welfare Benefits:

Beyond meat quality, silvopastoral grazing contributes to broader environmental and animal welfare goals:

- **Reduces wildfire risk** by controlling and removing flammable understory biomass through grazing.
- **Enhances biodiversity**, as the movement and grazing behavior of sheep help maintain ecological balance, while their feces naturally fertilize the soil.
- **Promotes animal welfare:** Life in wooded meadows mimics a semi-natural environment, lowering stress levels (in the absence of predators) and ensuring high welfare standards.

HIGHLIGHTS:

Sheep meat from animals grazing on forest meadows exhibits several nutritional advantages compared to meat from intensively reared animals

- **A higher percentage of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), contributing to improved nutritional value.**
- **A lower concentration of malondialdehyde (MDA), indicating enhanced oxidative stability and reduced risk of mutagenic compounds.**
- **Lower atherogenic (AI) and thrombogenic (TI) indices, suggesting a reduced risk of cardiovascular disease.**

Flock of sheep in the forest of mount Timfristos Photo V. Lappa

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